

Effect of Marital Status on Quality of Life among Post-menopausal Women: A study from South India

Sony Varghese ¹, Philomina Joicy V J ², Kavadi Naresh ³, Rajeshwari L^{*4}

¹ BUPA David Lange Care Homes, Auckland, New Zealand, ^{*2,4} JSS Medical College, JSS Academy of Higher Education and Research, Mysuru, India, ³ JSS College of Physiotherapy, Mysuru
^{*4} corresponding author: Rajeshwari L

Abstract: Menopause is the stage of life when oestrogen and progesterone secretion decreases and menstrual cycles cease. The physiological process of traversing menopause is complicated and is frequently accompanied by the side effects of ageing and social adjustment. Many clinical manifestations have been attributed to menopause and prevalence rates of symptoms, such as vasomotor dysfunctions, vaginal dryness, sleep disturbance, urinary complaints, and mood changes, vary greatly. At times, these symptoms were normalised as concomitants of the time of life and not addressed further. The menopause exert a negative impact on Quality of Life, adjusting for menopausal symptoms and sociodemographic factors. In this cross-sectional, comparative study, we analysed the quality of life among married and unmarried women in the postmenopausal phase. Menopause Specific Quality of Life Questionnaire (MENQOL) was employed among total of 50 post-menopausal women categorised equally into married and unmarried group. In this present study we found that the post-menopausal quality of life of unmarried subjects are poor when compared with the married subjects. This imparts to the importance of physical and psychological support to the women to cope up with post-menopausal symptoms.

Keywords: Menopause, Menopause Specific Quality of Life, Married, Unmarried, post-menopausal symptoms

I. INTRODUCTION

Menopause is characterized by the permanent cessation of menstruation, determined after 12 months of amenorrhea from the final menstrual period. As the women progress through various stages of menopause, from menopausal transition to post-menopause, many hormonal changes occur including increased follicle stimulating hormone levels (FSH), and depletion of oestrogen levels. [1] Menopause typically occurs between ages 46 and 52 years. Symptoms associated with menopause can emerge during a gradual transition period called perimenopause which begins when the first onset of irregular menses occurs. Many women experience an intensification of menopausal symptoms when they enter the late perimenopausal stage, which can impact quality of life. [2] Menopausal women experience a range of symptoms which exist in four broad categories (i) vasomotor (e.g., hot flashes, night sweats); (ii) somatic / physical (e.g., head and body aches, fatigue); (iii) psychological (e.g., anxiety, depression, memory and concentration problems) and (iv) sexual (e.g., vaginal dryness and reduced libido). Around 85 % of menopausal women experience these symptoms. The most prevalent symptoms include sleep problems (50–76 %), urogenital symptoms (38–71 %), loss of libido (43–60 %), muscle and joint pain (32– 57 %), psychological problems (57–60 %), and hot flashes and night sweats (35–83 %). [3] Even similar results were obtained from Indian population too. [4, 5]

World Health Organization (WHO) defines the Quality of Life (QoL) as “the perceived position of an individual in life in the context of the cultural system and value systems in which they reside and concerning their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns.” Therefore, it is a wide-ranging concept affected by an individual’s physical and mental health, level of independence, relationships within society and to salient environmental features, which indicates that quality of life is subjective and multi-dimensional. [6] Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) is negatively impacted by menopausal symptoms in women. The symptoms associated with low quality of life may be upsetting when they arise in the context of women's important roles in the family, career, and society. Menopause symptoms can occasionally be disabling, unpleasant, and self-limiting. [7] The QOL was found to be impaired in 70.2% of study subjects. The psychological symptoms attributed 70.8% to the poor QOL. [5] Thus, menopausal women's quality of life is crucial, and management of menopausal symptoms uplifts the quality of life of women in postmenopausal phase. [7]

Like income and education, marital status also play significant role in all aspects of QOL. Being married can be a protective factor against physical, psychological, and social problems as the age increases. [8] Therefore this present comparative study aimed to evaluate the effect of marriage on Quality of Life among post-menopausal women in South India.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Sample Selection

The participants who are married and unmarried women, between the age group of 55-75 years, and self-reported as currently menopausal or post-menopausal were recruited. Women, who were pre-menopausal or pregnant, with thyroid related problems, suffering from any psychiatric problems, after hysterectomy, or taking any medications were excluded from the study.

This cross-sectional study was conducted in a heterogeneous population of menopausal women who are the residents of Angamaly, a town in Central Kerala, on a total of 50 subjects; categorized equally into married and unmarried group. Sampling Procedure was Stratified random sampling.

B. Ethical Consideration

The study protocol was approved by the institutional ethical committee of Little Flower Hospital and Research Centre, Angamaly and participants provided informed consent upon collecting the data.

C. Methodology

This cross-sectional study included 50 postmenopausal women. The data was collected using a two-part questionnaire. In Part 1, sociodemographic information were collected by using a structured questionnaire, and in Part 2, the postmenopausal symptoms were collected by a using self-administered, standard validated menopause-specific QOL (MENQOL) questionnaire. The MENQOL consists of a total of 29 items with a 6-point Likert-scale format. It consists of four domains of menopausal symptoms, as experienced over the last month: such as vasomotor (items 1–3), psychosocial (items 4–10), physical (items 11–26), and sexual (items 27–29). Items pertaining to a specific symptom are rated as present or not present, and if present, how bothersome on a 0- 6 scale. Non-endorsement of an item is scored a “1” and endorsement a “2,” plus the number of the particular rating, thus possible score on any item ranges from one to eight. Means are calculated for each subscale by dividing the sum of the domain’s items by the number of items within that domain. The scores of 4 menopausal domains constituted a compound (total) score of QOL of postmenopausal women. [9]

D. Statistical Analysis

All data were entered into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0 version) for analysis. Descriptive statistics of the data were presented as frequencies, percentages and mean \pm SD. Comparison of MENQOL among groups was done using Mann Whitney U test. P-value of 0.05 or less was interpreted as significant for the analysis.

III. RESULTS

The present study was conducted on total number of 50 postmenopausal women belonging to the age group of 55-75 years, in which 25 were married and 25 were unmarried. The mean age of married and unmarried subjects was 62.84 ± 5.68 years and 60.44 ± 6.21 years respectively.

Table 1 shows the mean score of different domains of MENQOL questionnaire and the statistical analysis of comparing the mean scores among the study group by using Mann Whitney U test. The mean score of vasomotor domain was 2.25 ± 1.78 in married group and 1.79 ± 0.98 in unmarried. Even though, the score is more for married women in comparison with unmarried women, it did not reach statistical significance as the p value > 0.05 . Under psychosocial domain, the mean score was 2.18 ± 1 in married group and 3.31 ± 1 in unmarried group. It has proven that married women experience less psychological issue than unmarried women after menopause and it has reached significance level since p value < 0.05 . Likewise, the mean score of physical domain was 1.86 ± 0.69 in married and 2.32 ± 0.42 in unmarried, suggesting unmarried women suffers more physical difficulty than married women. But in comparison among study groups, the

difference didn't reach significance. In contrast, the mean score of sexual domain was same, ie. 1 ± 0 in both the groups. The lesser score shows that subjects experience less menopause related sexual symptoms irrespective of their marital status. The lower score in all the domains of the both group suggesting that the problems associated with post-menopausal phase were not much bothersome among study groups. The total score of MENQOL was 7.32 ± 2.69 and 8.42 ± 2.31 in married and unmarried group respectively. It indicate that quality of life after menopause is poor among unmarried women in comparison with married women, even if it did not reach significance.

TABLE 1
MEAN SCORE OF DIFFERENT DOMAINS OF MENQOL QUESTIONNAIRE AMONG THE STUDY GROUPS

Group	MENQOL Domain				Total score
	Mean \pm SD				
	Vasomotor	Psychosocial	Physical	Sexual	
Married (n=25)	2.25 ± 1.78	2.18 ± 1	1.86 ± 0.69	1 ± 0	7.32 ± 2.69
Unmarried (n=25)	1.79 ± 0.98	3.31 ± 1	2.32 ± 8.42	1 ± 0	8.42 ± 2.31
Comparison of the mean score by Mann Whitney U test					
	Vasomotor	Psychosocial	Physical	Sexual	Total score
Z VALUE	-0.465	-3.720	-1.845	0.000	-1.872
P VALUE	0.642	.000	0.065	1	0.061

Mann Whitney U test, $P < 0.05$ are considered to be statistically significant

IV. DISCUSSION

Menopause is the time of life when menstrual cycles cease, and is caused by significant reduction in secretion of the ovarian hormones like oestrogen and progesterone. Despite the fact that menopause is a natural event for women, each person's experience is unique, and some women seek medical guidance to manage their symptoms. [10] It's been estimated the mean age at menopause in Indian regions, varies between 45.5 years in North India and 47.8 years in the Central parts of India [11] The Indian Menopause Society, located in New Delhi reported that there are currently 65 million women over the menopausal age in India affected with menopausal symptoms. Women spend the last third of their lifetime in menopause, after their reproductive years have ended. During menopause, women experience different kind of symptoms and conditions related to changes in sex hormone levels and aging. The menopausal transition is typified by hot flashes and nocturnal sweats in addition to irregular monthly cycles and is exhibited few years preceding menopause. After menopause, genitourinary symptoms predominate, like vulvovaginal atrophy, dryness, and lower urinary tract symptoms, including urinary frequency, urgency, and nocturia, etc. [12] Due to these symptoms, 15-20% of menopausal women face difficulties in their quality of life. [13]

A study from Haryana, India has shown that prevalence of menopausal symptoms was found to be 87.7%. Majority of the study subjects had anxiety (80%), followed by physical and mental exhaustion (71.5%), sleep problem (61.2%), irritability (60.7%), Joint and muscular discomfort (56%) and heart problems (54%). The most classical symptom of menopause i.e., hot flushes were reported in 36.7%. The QOL was impaired in 70.2% of study subjects. The psychological symptoms attributed 70.8% to the poor QOL. [5] Another study from Puduchery, India has reported vasomotor symptoms were found in 80% of our study group, psychosocial symptoms were found in 93.2%, physical symptoms were found in 99% and sexual symptoms were found in 82%. [14] From the previous studies, it is evident that majority of the women under menopause experience more psychological difficulties which can seriously affect their mental

wellbeing and thus can cause reduction in the quality of life. It is further supported by the findings of the present study, that unmarried women experience more psychosocial stress than married women after menopause. And it has reached statistical significance. In this scenario, our study aimed to assess the effect of marital life on quality of life of a postmenopausal women. As per the results of the current study, it's found that quality of life is better among married than unmarried postmenopausal women. Low QOL among unmarried may be due to lack of a partner or family, feeling of loneliness and social support, etc. Especially in south India, where marriage is considered as a social norm, it will be difficult for a single person to stay away from marriage and stand-alone against a society. This further increases the pressure level along with feeling of solitude. Marital status and socioeconomic status is significant in determining quality of life factors for single persons. The rising percentage of unmarried individuals is one of the major contemporary societal trends. According to perspective of this generation, financial independence and hardships of family life outweighs the personal and social commitments. And their choice of life, inclines towards staying as single forever. While discussing about individuals who do not prefer a married life, they can consider of having a companion in their life, which can be a family member or a friend or a pet. The inner connection involved in the relationship can alleviate the psychological stress to a greater extend. A community based study with larger sample size is recommended further, taking into consideration of other options of companionship.

Other symptoms can be greatly reduced by menopausal hormonal therapy, diet modification, personal counselling, and participation in social activities, etc. Since a lot of women have a negative outlook concerning menopause, educating them about a variety of topics, such as an overview of the condition, its coping mechanisms, dietary habits, and body relaxation techniques, could be crucial to helping them accept the phase and enhance their quality of life during it. In parallel, engaging in aerobic exercise and regular physical activity can enhance various aspects of life quality. It has been shown that menopausal women can improve and enhance their quality of life by using food supplements including soy, licorice, red clover, and fish oil, as well as herbal remedies that contain phytoestrogens and isoflavones. Given that menopausal women's testosterone levels would normally decline, this could result in a drop in excitation, sexual response, and desire. It is therefore advised to use phytoestrogen products. Red clover consumption has been shown to raise luteinizing hormone, lower sex-hormone-binding globulin, raise testosterone, and raise blood estradiol levels. It may also lessen the intensity of hot flashes and alleviate vaginal dryness and dyspareunia symptoms. Compared to other herbal remedies, particularly soy and red clover, licorice becomes effective more quickly. In addition to these products, topical application of royal jelly, which has pseudo-estrogenic properties, may help reduce sexual difficulties and enhance menopausal women's quality of life. [15]

V. CONCLUSION

Menopause is an unavoidable phase of women's life. Many clinical manifestations have been attributed to menopause which include domains of vasomotor, psychosocial, sexual and physical. The disruption in mental and physical wellbeing of life can significantly reduce the quality of life in a postmenopausal women. The present study conducted on married and unmarried women under post menopause has shown that the quality of life of an unmarried women is compromised when compared to a married women. Thus this attempt, gives an insight into a fact that being married or having a companion in life can alleviate the condition to a certain extent, especially to reduce psychosocial difficulties. Alongside, menopausal hormonal therapy, diet modification, personal counselling, and participation in social activities, etc. are suggested to improve their life.

REFERENCES

- [1] Carter, E., Bruinvels, G., Timmins, K., Pedlar, C., & Martin, D. (2024). Menopausal symptoms, exercise practices, and advice received in active women: a multi-country survey of strava app users. *Women & health*, 64(1), 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03630242.2023.2284730>
- [2] Chow, H., Righton, O., Berry, H., Bell, Z., & Flynn, A. C. (2024). A systematic review of community pharmacy interventions to improve peri- and post-menopausal health. *Post reproductive health*, 20533691231223681. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20533691231223681>

- [3] Monteleone, P., Mascagni, G., Giannini, A., Genazzani, A. R., & Simoncini, T. (2018). Symptoms of menopause - global prevalence, physiology and implications. *Nature reviews. Endocrinology*, 14(4), 199–215. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrendo.2017.180>
- [4] Bairy, L., Adiga, S., Bhat, P., & Bhat, R. (2009). Prevalence of menopausal symptoms and quality of life after menopause in women from South India. *The Australian & New Zealand journal of obstetrics & gynaecology*, 49(1), 106–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1479-828X.2009.00955.x>
- [5] Kalhan, M., Singhania, K., Choudhary, P., Verma, S., Kaushal, P., & Singh, T. (2020). Prevalence of Menopausal Symptoms and its Effect on Quality of Life among Rural Middle Aged Women (40-60 Years) of Haryana, India. *International journal of applied & basic medical research*, 10(3), 183–188. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijabmr.IJABMR_428_19
- [6] The World Health Organization Quality of Life assessment (WHOQOL): position paper from the World Health Organization. (1995). *Social science & medicine* (1982), 41(10), 1403–1409. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(95\)00112-k](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(95)00112-k)
- [7] Huang, Y., Chatooh, N. D., Qi, T., Wang, G., Ma, L., Ying, Q., Lan, Y., Song, Y., Li, C., Chu, K., Chen, P., Xu, W., Wan, H., Cai, Y., & Zhou, J. (2018). Health-related quality of life and its associated factors in Chinese middle-aged women. *Climacteric: the journal of the International Menopause Society*, 21(5), 483–490. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13697137.2018.1476133>
- [8] Moudi, A., Shahinfar, S., Razmara, M. R., & Salehiniya, H. (2020). Is the quality of life different in single and remarried elderly?. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 9, 44. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_613_19
- [9] Radtke, J. V., Terhorst, L., & Cohen, S. M. (2011). The Menopause-Specific Quality of Life Questionnaire: psychometric evaluation among breast cancer survivors. *Menopause (New York, N.Y.)*, 18(3), 289–295. <https://doi.org/10.1097/gme.0b013e3181ef975a>
- [10] Nelson H. D. (2008). Menopause. *Lancet (London, England)*, 371(9614), 760–770. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(08\)60346-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(08)60346-3)
- [11] Prasad, J. B., Tyagi, N. K., & Verma, P. (2021). Age at menopause in India: A systematic review. *Diabetes & metabolic syndrome*, 15(1), 373–377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsx.2021.01.013>
- [12] Takahashi, T. A., & Johnson, K. M. (2015). Menopause. *The Medical clinics of North America*, 99(3), 521–534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcna.2015.01.006>
- [13] Martin, K. A., & Manson, J. E. (2008). Approach to the patient with menopausal symptoms. *The Journal of clinical endocrinology and metabolism*, 93(12), 4567–4575. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2008-1272>
- [14] G K, P., & Arounassalame, B. (2013). The quality of life during and after menopause among rural women. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research : JCDR*, 7(1), 135–139. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2012/4910.2688>
- [15] Taebi, M., Abdollahian, S., Ozgoli, G., Ebadi, A., & Kariman, N. (2018). Strategies to improve menopausal quality of life: A systematic review. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 7, 93. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_137_17